

CMIP7 Use Case Synthesis for EDS+

Using CMIP data, improving the NERC Environmental Data Service

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This document supports the [EDS+ CMIP7 Use Case](#) project report.

This report is a synthesis of a series of interviews that were held to understand how CMIP data is used and is going to be used by the UK research community. We ask what features of CMIP attracts people to use it and what are the obstacles that are run into when using and accessing CMIP data; how the UK research community engages in the CMIP development process; what tools and workflows would be valuable to improve CMIP data access and useability.

The interviews lasted about an hour and we asked questions around 5 key themes:

- How CMIP data is used by the UK research community.
- Positive features that attract people to use CMIP data.
- What makes it difficult to use CMIP data?
- Opportunities for the research community to better engage with CMIP.
- Anything else they would like us to know about.

Interviewees

We held conversations with a number of CMIP data users at various research institutions and points in their career to gain an understanding of what the community feels could be improved about the CMIP data service and obstacles to CMIP data access.

Experienced CMIP users

We interviewed 7 experienced researchers, who prepare and use CMIP data. Their research interests covered historical climate, decadal climate projections, European wintertime weather, aerosols and atmospheric chemistry, stratospheric ozone, regional emissions, and teleconnections. They worked with the following models: HadGEM3, EC-EARTH, UKCA, and UKESM1.

Early Career Researchers (ECRs)

We interviewed 4 early career researchers who were all users of CMIP data. Their research covered historical climate and future climate scenarios, cloud feedbacks, large scale circulation changes, atmospheric dynamics, jet stream behaviour, interrogating model biases, sulphur dioxide and aerosol formation.

How CMIP data is used by the UK research community.

Key Points

- Data is accessed via JASMIN (i) directly and worked with on JASMIN in group workspaces or (ii) pulled off JASMIN to home institution
- Used for model intercomparison
- Used as a benchmark to analyse typical models
- Data that is not on JASMIN is downloaded directly from ESGF
- The range of research areas CMIP was used for included: atmospheric chemistry, model development, historical climate, winter weather, atmospheric dynamics, model intercomparison
- Use JASMIN jupyter notebook service for data processing
- Use google drive to share work internationally to those without access to JASMIN

Experienced CMIP users

Model intercomparison and climate science

- CMIP data is used to understand and document climate model progress and evaluate climate models to build confidence in model predictions. Almost everyone who uses climate models is interested in some process or other.
- For CMIP7, interested in projections - similar analysis to CMIP6 but taking advantage of improved capability of the models
- Exploring inter-model diversity

Model development and running simulations

- Produces CMIP data for AerChemMIP
- Model development and evaluation
- NGMS (Next Generation Modelling System)
- Model development - comparing UKESM1 to observations and other models
- Lots more work to do with CMIP6, currently running regional aerosol MIP that falls between CMIP6 and CMIP7 run under CMIP6 protocols

CMIP work using JASMIN

- When the data was new, it was pulled off MASS before it even made it to the ESGF archive, not necessarily CMORised at that stage
- Relying on shared data resources these days (accessed via JASMIN) rather than downloading multiple copies of data from the CMIP archive.
- Initial analysis of CMIP6 data on JASMIN
- Do analysis on JASMIN and can point others to scripts on JASMIN when working collaboratively (in UK)
- Use JASMIN jupyter notebook service

- Get CMIP6 data from JASMIN, views CEDA disk as a local disk and runs script reads data from the CEDA archive. Then outputs post-processed files to group workspace
- Do data analysis on IDL on JASMIN, and use LOTUS, noticed higher use of JASMIN has made it slower

Downloading data

- For CMIP5, had to download own data
- Eventually it became more convenient to download data to local servers
- Downloaded data that wasn't part of the JASMIN subset from ESGF

Collaboration

- A lot of work ends up on Google drive when collaborating internationally to make it accessible to those without access to JASMIN

ECR's

Model intercomparison and climate science

- Used as a benchmark to analyse typical models
- Used for model intercomparison
- In future will use to analyse how well synoptic processes are represented in CMIP models - will involve wind fields precipitation fields, pressure, temp at high resolution
- Just using CMIP in next 6 months when seems appropriate
- Investigating model projections, how the jet stream might change in the future, interrogating models in terms of their biases - what they get right and wrong with respect to observed climate. Using many models with slightly different ways of representing sub-grid scale processes as a multi-model ensemble to answer science questions e.g. how does greater warming at polar latitudes affect the jet stream.

CMIP work using JASMIN/CEDA archive

- Retrieved data through JASMIN accessed from CEDA platform
- Use JASMIN group work spaces to analyse the data
- Works on JASMIN exclusively
- Made requests for a lot of specific data not on CEDA archive

Own institution computers for CMIP processing and analysis

- Data processing and analysis done on own institution computers - for ease of collaboration, colleagues not on JASMIN
- Uses shared storage at their own institution where lots of data has already been downloaded. Also uses JASMIN. Very specific data is downloaded directly from ESGF node.

Positive features that attract people to use CMIP data.

Key Points

- metadata rich and consistent from CF-NetCDF format
- standard file formats makes data easy to use and lots of tools available for analysing netCDF data
- CMORisation and standard structure of archive
- easy access from JASMIN and analysis from JASMIN means size is not an issue, also easy to download subsets from JASMIN
- “JASMIN, it’s like the air, if it went away it would be a real problem”
- “Access by disk is by far the best solution”
- also easy to download from ESGF
- multi-model
- “the best thing there is” for understanding climate change on a global scale and capturing the full range of model uncertainty
- standardised variables with lots of metadata, including documenting how data was converted from raw data
- CEDA archive useful as a central data store all in one place to use different data interchangeably (e.g. FAAM, CMIP, ERA-5)
- there is a lot of data available
- Easy to find the data, all on ESGF and JASMIN has large subset
- CEDA data request for specific variables has been very useful when data need that is not already on JASMIN
- - a large number of models do the same core simulations making it great for model intercomparison
- JASMIN has been transformative in enabling science
- easy to share work internationally by giving user access to shared gws on JASMIN for collaboration
- contact email included within files very useful
- ES-DOC very useful and available at same time as data from modelling centre (no peer review delay) but underutilised

Experienced CMIP users

Ease of use of data and tools

- CMIP data gets easier to use with each cycle
- Use CMIP data as a teaching resource (AI for ER course)
- Lots of tools for analysing CF-NetCDF data: IRIS, CF Python, cdo, matlab, jupyter notebooks
- CF Python tools are working well
- Straightforward to set up new colleagues with using CMIP data (except watching out for differences between models)

- ES-DOC very useful as documents not peer reviewed, so can be published at the same time as data and is directly from the modelling centre. But this service was underutilised
- Download scripts for ESGF were great but difficult to customise

Standardised metadata and file structure

- Standardised data makes analysis more straightforward
- Metadata structure, file formats, various tools make it easy to use
- Checked, consistent metadata in header
- Good documentation - data is shared along with necessary core metadata
- “Cf conventions are fantastic”
- Data from lots of centres in same format - CMORisation very useful and standardised structure of the archives
- Within files there is a contact email included - very useful if notice any issues or want to ask something about the data
- Quality control for CMIP6 quite good - much better than CMIP5

Valuable multi-model resource, a large amount of data for intercomparison

- Systematic, coordinated, multi-model (lots of models not just a handful), Big
- Can compare lots of different models
- There is nothing else like it
- Great tool for evaluating model and model inter-comparison
- It's completeness - a large number of models all doing a set of core simulations and save a lot of useful diagnostics making it great for model intercomparison and quite a unique resource for this (and most also do the tier 2 and 3 experiments too)
- Homogeneity in data - as well as a number of diagnostics provided on native grids, a set of data from each model have been processed onto a common set of grids making the data easy to use
- As model developers, model intercomparison available from CMIP is very useful for evaluating their model - especially as earth system models get more complicated. Common experimental protocol very useful, some of models in project are specifically designed to enable understanding of why models differ, figuring out sensitivity to certain parameters etc.

JASMIN computing resources used for data access

- Access to data in the CEDA archive directly via JASMIN analysis machine
- “JASMIN, it's like the air, if it went away it would be a real problem”
- Don't have to download data that is on JASMIN, can access from there
- JASMIN is a useful resource for analysing large data volumes
- Great that students have access to JASMIN - valuable lessons for using a big HPC unit
- Data on JASMIN - can use scripts to take annual or zonal means and then pull the necessary data to local storage space (rather than downloading full data)
- Useful that the Met Office have access to JASMIN

- “Access by disk is by far the best solution”
- JASMIN has been transformative in enabling science
- Accessing CEDA copy locally has massively improved workflow, as well as being able to request CEDA to download particular variables, meant only having to keep a local copy of very specialist variables. This helped with space constraints
- Easy to set up with new colleagues and share with colleagues via JASMIN - can give access to GWS on JASMIN to international collaborators to allow sharing of data

ECR's

Ease of use of data and tools

- Easy to find the data - all on ESGF, JASMIN has large subset, can just search for the data you need
- Easy to retrieve the data from JASMIN

Standardised metadata and file structure

- Net-cdf format is metadata rich, metadata fairly solid
- Standard format - all netCDF making it easy to use
- Consistent variable names and variables well documented in metadata
- Documented how data converted from raw data, makes it easier to get back to raw data to check and re-do calculations

Valuable multi-model resource, a large amount of data for intercomparison

- CMIP is “the best thing there is” for understanding climate change on a global scale and capturing the full range of model uncertainty
- Only tool like it available for their work
- Where building on work already done, can use same datasets - don't have to do everything from scratch
- There's a lot of data 'zoo of MIPs' within CMIP to investigate any question you want to look at, wide range of variables on a range of timescales

Data access

- CEDA archive useful as a central data store all in one place to use different data interchangeably (e.g. FAAM, CMIP, ERA-5)

What makes it difficult to use CMIP data?

Key Points

- data sizes -too large, takes weeks to download, starting to only be accessible if using centralised compute centres like JASMIN
- data on JASMIN is not all the data available
- finding relevant information (e.g. variable definitions, understanding directory structures) without searching for relevant papers - would be useful if this info was linked to at top level page
- difficult to pull all data for one variable - have to click through each model - better batch download tools would be useful
- CMIP data availability incompatible with IPCC timeframes and CCMI. for IPCC AR6 this meant a lot of the data used was CMIP5 and papers published with CMIP6 data only included the data that was available at the time and were written in a hurry. These quick high-level papers blocked more detailed publications on important IPCC topics.
- heterogeneity in data - incompatible time calendars, irregular grids, errors in data - time consuming to do own QC to check data, errors may be missed when computing bulk statistics
- issues with download from ESGF - sometimes system is down, difficult to download large amounts of data, search engine doesn't work with too many filters, have to download full 4D fields unlike data on JASMIN where you can take a subset
- model documentation sometimes does not include essential information about e.g. processes, modules included in a findable way
- if model physics not well documented, difficult to distinguish whether there is structural uncertainty between models or it is just noise, makes some model data unusable.
- CMIP5 withdrew and replaced many datasets with issues - meant there were papers published on previous data that no longer exists
- sometimes difficult to know whether files are missing or not produced intentionally (e.g. specific set of ensemble members)
- disconnect between centres about standard conventions - e.g. ensemble model physics code used differently by different centres which is not well documented.
- For model intercomparison, only half models are on BADC

Experienced CMIP users

CMIP timeline inconsistent with IPCC and CCMI

- CMIP data availability incompatible with IPCC timeframes: used raw model data for historical HadGEM simulations before fully processed (CMOR-ised) data was available
- Disconnect between CCMI and CMIP, timescales don't align, running almost identical runs again

- IPCC AR6 and CMIP6 timelines not well aligned, short timeframe between when CMIP6 data was made available and IPCC AR6. This meant some topics that were very important to IPCC were done in a hurry rather than in depth to meet the deadlines and only included the CMIP6 data available at the time. This also meant these shorter high-level papers published quickly blocked more detailed publications using the full CMIP6 datasets. AR6 ended up mostly based on CMIP5 because the deadlines were so tight.

Space issues with large data

- CMIP data “chunks” can sometimes be too large for direct use in analysis tools
- Worry that CMIP7 is going to be bigger
- Large data volumes are borderline incompatible with being able to download for local analysis.
- Data space - improved by access to JASMIN
- Memory limitations that apply to the jupyter notebook service sometimes makes exploratory analysis difficult - unclear how much memory is available and how much has been used, kernel unexpectedly dies. Some analysis too large for these notebooks to cope with

Data access issues

- Forgetting that the CMIP data that can be accessed via JASMIN is only a small part of the full CMIP dataset
- On the web interface, it is easy to find a particular field from a particular model but more difficult to gather all model data for one variable at once, much easier to just pull off JASMIN. Metagrid - rewrite of interface to make it easier coming soon (aims2.llnl.gov)
- Not always straightforward to know what data is on JASMIN for each model, wrote own script to find this out in the end.
- When workspaces get shut down, have to re-download the data all over again

Data availability

- Don't have all the variables you want from some models
- For model intercomparison, only half models are on BADC, have to download the data for the rest from the ESGF node - takes a lot of time and space
- When downloading from ESGF node, have to download the full 4D field data from each model (which becomes very large), if the data was on JASMIN you could just take zonal means and pull that to your GWS which saves a lot of space and time
- International collaboration is difficult, a modelling centre might have done a set of experiments but difficult to collaborate when the data has not yet been mirrored

Information about data difficult to find

- struggle to find various variable definitions without papers that specifically describe them. Collection here: metoffice.github.io/arise-cmor-tables/ (not always clear what the variable is from the longname alone).

- Lots of different behaviour in CMIP for sampling structural uncertainty - but if model physics not well documented then can't tell if this is structural uncertainty or just noise - have to leave models out when information not clear/available
- Disconnect between some centres on how they use the standard names e.g. physics code in ensemble members used differently by each centre which isn't well documented. (For example, the GISS model has 3 physics versions indicated by p1, p3, p5 which should be analysed separately but they are all under the same model name. This information is explained in model paper but not in files themselves and may be easily missed in analysis.) Needs to be well documented or agreed that runs with very different physics need different model names e.g. CESM has different model versions for different physics.
- ES-DOC underutilised - difficult to find specific information from each modelling centre - what processes are included, modules included, etc. CMIP6 documentation is better than previous CMIPs but some models just cite previous CMIP papers as documentation. Model papers are held up by peer review - particularly for CMIP5.
- Sometimes it is difficult to know whether files are missing or were not produced intentionally. Would be useful to know which ensemble members a modelling centre has chosen to produce (e.g. just r1, r3, r5 etc.) documented in file or readme's

Data processing

- Inconsistency between number of dimensions between variables, e.g. not all single level coordinates have z dimension, makes it more difficult to re-use analysis code
- Converting model output to CMIP data format is challenging, would prefer if there were more configurable tools for doing this.
- "The hardest thing (after building the model and making forcing files) is converting the data"
- Data processing - have all tools needed but had to learn best ways of working through trial and error, would be great to have training on optimising data analysis techniques

Data inconsistencies

- There is some data that doesn't follow the established norms, coding exceptions to account for that can be time consuming ("hours and hours"). E.g. met office 360 day year.
- Quality control - some of the data is clearly wrong
- Errors in data that are not flagged, it would be useful if it could be communicated when data is updated to people who have already downloaded the data
- CMIP5 - lots of centres withdrew datasets meaning datasets were being withdrawn after use in publications - quality control was better for CMIP6

ECR's

Data inconsistencies

- Heterogeneity in data, issues or corruptions - mismatched time calendars - would be ideal if there was an agreed upon process for mapping that data to a consistent shared calendar format
- Poor quality control - even commonly used z500 one model had exactly same field for every year in January for every year, random days where geopotential height was a billion, relative humidity way over 100% in the arctic
- Extensive process of quality control to do which takes a lot of time
- Computing bulk statistics you are going to miss errors in data if you don't take the time to perform QC yourself
- Understanding where there are heterogeneities - currently get that info from other people who have encountered the problems

Information about data difficult to find

- Understanding directory structures, e.g. some models have different grids - in directory structure but not clear
- Experiment ensemble members - base member not always clear - may be 2 if 1 was a bad run - you have to go through each model individually to check which is the right one - would be good if it was clear when you download the data
- Takes time to find model documentation and specific papers with info about the data - a centralised hub of information would be useful
- Finding model data for a given variable takes a lot of time
- Reproducibility - 'data can be retrieved from the ESGF' on papers there is not sufficient information to reproduce the data

Space issues with large data

- Data size is a problem - solution is centralised compute - took several weeks to download all the data, file corrupted by a second of lost connection
- Could be a problem with size e.g. for undergraduates downloading data on their own laptop - as long as you download the data wisely is ok. Data storage has not been a problem when using JASMIN and shared storage. Can combine files and take averages rather than downloading everything

Data access

- Central compute sometimes painful compared to own institution
- Jupyter notebooks don't work well over remote connection - makes centralised computers difficult
- ESGF download causes problems, the tools available are not easily accessible
- downloading large volumes of ESGF data is difficult
- ESGF portal sometimes doesn't work - would be helpful if there was a message to notify when the service is down
- On ESGF search tool, if you add too many subset filters it doesn't give you any results when the data is there

- Would be useful if there was a better way to do a batch download of data - takes longer than it should do, or more clearly advertised tools to do this

Opportunities for the research community to better engage with CMIP

Key Points

- via own networks
- individual model conferences - can speak to contacts in community that feed back to overall CMIP process
- Fresh Eyes on CMIP for ECRs
- add a 'getting started' page
- add links to useful pages and documents at top level page
- CMIP process feels big and overwhelming, not sure how as a data user I can influence it
- CMIP7 workshop on UK contributions to CMIP7 has been well advertised
- good public consultation from CMIP IPO
- ESGF help emails
- lowering bar for climate data analysis - model specific info made available in central place so data is more accessible
- need training in out of memory data analysis

Experienced CMIP users

- Would engage with CMIP via own networks in the first instance
- How is the data request task team reaching out to different communities?
- Add a link to the CMIP IPO information pages from the EDS website.
- A getting started page (info about useful resources and how to find them)
- Point to pages/tables that clearly show what data is available at the top level (ESGF CMIP6 Data Holdings (Inl.gov))
- Need training in out of memory data analysis, best practices, the infrastructure available e.g. optimal chunking
- Lowering the bar for climate model data analysis - model specific information made available in a central place or forum so that the data is more accessible to lots of different users
- CMIP7 workshop next week - how UK contributes to CMIP7 - well advertised
- CMIP International Project Office - has good public consultation
- IPCC AR6 involvement with CMIP6
- Running regional aerosol MIP that falls between CMIP6 and CMIP7 timeframes but is still listed with CMIP6 IPO as being a MIP
- ESGF help emails

ECR's

- Fresh Eyes on CMIP task team <https://youtu.be/URXeIUP2zPY>
<https://wcrp-cmip.org/fresh-eyes-on-cmip/>
- Attending individual MIP conferences and speaking to contacts in the community who feed back into overall CMIP process
- Not really aware of opportunities to shape the process and not sure how as a data user they can have much input, feels very big, overwhelming
- Interested in shaping particular MIPs used for their research
- Incremental changes - models get a little bit better each round of CMIP but just limited improvements, maybe investing the resources in running less models at higher resolution - this is a challenge for CMIP moving forward

Other stuff

Experienced CMIP users

- How many people use the web interface vs. pulling data directly from ESGF with computers like JASMIN?
- MIP table development: working on a MIP table setup resource that would separate out generalised MIP table content (stuff you can probably leave alone) from project specific information (stuff you need to tweak).
- Advocate for more comprehensive model documentation - like was done for CMIP5 by metafor
- Recommend stringent QC for core diagnostics from the DECK
- Suggested a web tool for running own QC checks on example files.
- Concerned that increasing data volumes may become limiting
- A table that shows what CMIP data is on JASMIN and a search tool would be useful
- Problem of data sizes and data replication is a challenge everywhere with multi-centre science
- Some kind of communication that data has been updated where errors have been found would be useful e.g. an email sent out to all who have accessed the data, a forum
- ES-Doc - there is process for reporting errors in data, but it is quite separate from the directory where the data is
- Training on optimal practices with data analysis, efficient data processing
- cdo and nco are good tools but are 'black boxes' and quite fragile, if data is formatted slightly weird may not read your file, would be good for more people to have more control over data processing - training or shared forum would be useful
- A github for everyone to share their data analysis processes
- High memory jupyter notebooks would be great
- Would like a tape option for UKCA data once initially analysis of data on the disk is finished but would still like to access this data, feels wasteful and time-consuming to have to re-download it all over again
- GPU cluster being released - dedicated training on how to use this would be helpful

- Need to know - what emissions have been put into the model - is the model emissions driven or concentration driven. Technical information about certain schemes - what processes are included. Knowing the level of complexity is really important for understanding why the models behave the way they do
- When find issues with data - check with modelling centre first then report it
- Needs to be a balance between quality control slowing down data availability even more and improved quality of initial data. Experienced users have their own checks now to sanity check the data.
- Better community consultation about which CMIP data should be archived on CEDA - variables prioritised for what AR6 would need but might be good to extend further to e.g. large NERC national capability projects and what they might need
- Interesting to see what's being used by local users and what is being downloaded directly from ESGF to analyse which data would be best kept on CEDA

ECR's

- Add flags to certain files that have issues raised, (e.g. geopotential height is wrong) so that people can see this warning when they download the data and don't have to work it out individually
- Maybe create a small selection of python scripts to run with files you want to use that flags the errors that have come up with that data
- Can more information be in the CMIP webpage of the data collection or a top-level folder?
- Interested if any outputs of storm resolution models destiny, destination Earth, next gem and dyamond high resolution global runs are going to be archived on CEDA as part of next round of CMIP? Is parallel to CMIP and going to be engaged with in the coming 5 years
- Looking at CMIP data on CEDA archive Project Record: WCRP CMIP6: Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (ceda.ac.uk) you have to click through each model individually - would be useful to have all in one place which data is contained by each model a for each field and resolution
- A script to collect all models with data from a certain variable
- Parallel space for the community to submit scripts that CEDA could host where people say what worked for them and share scripts for accessing data
- Even one script example of how to retrieve e.g. 'the historical projections of surface temperature' from across the data, a script to collect one variable at one resolution from the data as an example to be used by others
- Too many models to cite individually - when referencing, thank modelling community as a whole and ESGF
- Would like pressure level ERA5 data on CEDA
- More public engagement to make people aware of the data available and the tools available to download it